

Report on the climate suitability analysis of *Elasmopalpus lignosellus*

Introduction

Climate suitability analysis allows risk assessors to identify regions where climate is likely to support the establishment of a pest (IPPC, 2013). This analysis is typically based on pest biology and/or distribution according to the different methodology/models available (Devorshak, 2012). Because of this, an extensive literature research, in accordance with EFSA systematic review methodology (EFSA, 2010), was performed to gather relevant information on the ecology, physiology, and distribution of the pest *Elasmopalpus lignosellus*. Then, the data extracted from the literature search were used to analyse the climate suitability of *Elasmopalpus lignosellus* in the EU.

Note to this report

This document includes a description of the methodology and results of the systematic literature search and climate suitability analysis developed in the context of the EFSA Scientific Opinion on *Elasmopalpus lignosellus* for the European Union (EFSA et al., 2023). For a complete discussion of results and, conclusions of the present analysis, please refer to the related Scientific Opinion cited above.

Methods

Systematic literature review

Searches were performed to identify relevant information on the ecology, physiology, and distribution of the pest *E. lignosellus*. Table 1 shows the list of databases that were consulted. Results from the scientific databases were crosschecked and integrated (if needed) with records of the from EPPO Global database¹ and CABI² databases.

Table 1: List of databases consulted for the extensive literature search

Databases	Platform
Web of Science Core Collection	Web of Science
Biosis	
CAB Abstracts	
Chinese Science Citation Database	
Current Content Connect	
FSTA- the food science resource	
Korean Journal Database	
Medline	
Russian Science Citation Index	
SciELO Citation Index	
Scopus	Scopus

The scientific and international common names of the pest, retrieved from EPPO Global database¹, CABI², and SINAVIMO³, were used as keywords to interrogate the bibliographic databases. No other

¹ <https://gd.eppo.int/>

² <https://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/>

³ <https://www.sinavimo.gob.ar/plaga/elasmopalpus-lignosellus>

keywords were used (e.g., “biology”, “physiology”, “temperature”, “distribution”, etc...) not to limit the retrieval of documents useful for the purposes of this search.

Table 2: Taxonomy, EPPO Code and main hosts of *Elasmopalpus lignosellus*.

Scientific name	<i>Elasmopalpus lignosellus</i> (Zell.)
Other scientific names (CABI, SINAVIMO)	<i>Pempelia lignosella</i> (Zell.) <i>Salebria lignosella</i> (Zell.) <i>Dasyphyga carbonella</i> (Hulst) <i>Elasmopalpus tartarella</i> (Zell.) <i>Elasmopalpus major</i> (Zell.) <i>Elasmopalpus anthracellus</i> (Ragonot) <i>Elasmopalpus carbonella</i> (Hulst) <i>Elasmopalpus puer</i> (Dyar) <i>Elasmopalpus incautella</i> (Zell.)
International common names	lesser cornstalk borer, kleiner maisstengelbohrer, elasmopalpus, lagarta do colo do milho, lagarta elasmopalpus, barrenador menor del maíz, barrenador menor del tallo de maíz, gusano perforador del brote, taladrador menor, barrenador gusano saltarin, gusano saltarin, sprout hole worm, lesser stem borer, broca do colo, sugarcane jumping borer, barrenador del cuello, barrenador menor, coralillo, gusano picador de la hoja, taladrador de la raíz, oruguita taladradora de la cana de azucar, taladrador menor del tallo del maíz y arroz, pyrale du maïs et du riz
Taxonomy	Kingdom: <i>Animalia</i> Phylum: <i>Arthropoda</i> Class: <i>Insecta</i> Order: <i>Lepidoptera</i> Family: <i>Pyralidae</i>
EPPO Code	ELASI
Crop hosts	Polyphagous, including plants in the Poaceae and Fabaceae families

Error! Reference source not found. shows the query syntax used in Web of Science and Scopus platforms, the date of the search and the number of documents obtained.

Table 3: Search strings used to interrogate the bibliographic databases

Platform	Set	Date of search	Query	Number of documents
Web of Science	#2	14/09/2022	TS=(“ <i>Elasmopalpus lignosellus</i> ” OR “ <i>Pempelia lignosella</i> ” OR “ <i>Salebria lignosella</i> ” OR “ <i>Dasyphyga carbonella</i> ” OR “ <i>Elasmopalpus tartarella</i> ” OR “ <i>Elasmopalpus major</i> ” OR “ <i>Elasmopalpus anthracellus</i> ” OR “ <i>Elasmopalpus carbonella</i> ” OR “ <i>Elasmopalpus puer</i> ” OR “ <i>Elasmopalpus incautella</i> ” OR “Lesser cornstalk borer” OR “kleiner Maisstengelbohrer” OR “Lagarta do colo do milho” OR “Lagarta elasmopalpus” OR “Barrenador menor del maíz” OR “Barrenador menor del tallo de maíz” OR “Gusano perforador del brote” OR “Taladrador menor” OR “Barrenador gusano saltarin” OR “Gusano saltarin” OR “Sprout hole worm” OR “Lesser stem borer” OR “Broca do colo” OR “Sugarcane jumping borer” OR “barrenador del cuello” OR “barrenador menor” OR “coralillo” OR “gusano picador de la hoja” OR “taladrador de la raíz” OR “oruguita taladradora de la cana de azucar” OR “taladrador menor del tallo del maíz y arroz” OR “pyrale du maïs et du riz”)	414
SCOPUS	#2	14/09/2022	TITLE-ABS-KEY (“ <i>Elasmopalpus lignosellus</i> ” OR “ <i>Pempelia lignosella</i> ” OR “ <i>Salebria lignosella</i> ” OR “ <i>Dasyphyga carbonella</i> ” OR “ <i>Elasmopalpus tartarella</i> ” OR “ <i>Elasmopalpus major</i> ” OR “ <i>Elasmopalpus anthracellus</i> ” OR “ <i>Elasmopalpus carbonella</i> ” OR “ <i>Elasmopalpus puer</i> ” OR “ <i>Elasmopalpus incautella</i> ” OR “Lesser cornstalk borer” OR “kleiner Maisstengelbohrer” OR “Lagarta do colo do milho” OR “Lagarta elasmopalpus” OR “Barrenador menor del maíz” OR “Barrenador menor del tallo de maíz” OR “Gusano perforador del brote” OR “Taladrador menor” OR “Barrenador gusano saltarin” OR “Gusano saltarin” OR “Sprout hole worm” OR “Lesser stem borer” OR “Broca do colo” OR “Sugarcane jumping borer” OR “barrenador del cuello” OR “barrenador menor” OR “coralillo” OR “gusano picador de la hoja” OR “taladrador de la raíz” OR “oruguita taladradora de la cana de azucar” OR “taladrador menor del tallo del maíz y arroz” OR “pyrale du maïs et du riz”)	60

All the references were exported to the reference manager software EndoNoteX9 (The EndNote Team, 2013) and checked for duplicates. The documents coming from grey literature (Google Scholar, National extension services reports, etc.) were added to the scientific references coming from the database and screened.

Document screening

Document screening was performed on the software DistillerSR (Evidence Partners, 2022) and followed a two-step approach. In both steps the documents were screened answering the question “*Is there any information on physiology, ecology, and distribution of the pest?*”.

The screenshot displays the 'Reference Details' section of the DistillerSR software. It shows a reference entry with the following information: ID 83, title 'Attack by the lesser cornstalk borer *Elasmopalpus lignosellus* (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) in sugarcane', authors 'Salvatore, A. R., Lopez, G., Acosta, M., Alamo, F., Willink, E.', year '2008', and a DOI link. Below the reference, there are 'Full Text Links' with a 'DOI.org' button and 'Reference Label(s)' with a 'WoS_Scopus' button. The main content area shows the abstract text: 'In Tucuman, Argentina, sugarcane is attacked, during its sprouting period (from October to November) by, among other pests, the lesser cornstalk borer *Elasmopalpus lignosellus*. The borer also attacks various other important crops in the region. The biology of the pest is outlined, and the damage that it causes described. Its occurrence is associated with poor and sandy soils, dry conditions and temperatures over 27°C. This paper reports a study on the percentage of shoots attacked by the pest under 3 cultural practices: conventional dryland cropping - harvesting without trash cover; conventional cropping but with irrigation; and with stubble - harvesting green cane with stubble cover left in place. Assessments were made in October and November in 2004-06 at 13 localities in the province. Percentage attack by the pest was 24.05% over the 13 localities under conventional cropping, but was reduced 0.18% (over 10 localities) and to zero (over 7 localities) in the irrigated and green harvesting with stubble treatments, respectively.' To the right of the abstract is a 'Submit Form' button and a dropdown menu set to 'Datarama order'. Below this is a question: '1. Is there any information on physiology, ecology and distribution of the pest?' with three buttons: 'Yes', 'No', and 'Unclear'. A second question follows: '2. Specify what type of information' with three buttons: 'Physiology/Ecology', 'Distribution', and 'Others', each with a corresponding input field.

Figure 1: Title and Abstract Screening, Screenshot from DistillerSR (DistillerSR. Version 2.35. Evidence Partners; 2021. Accessed September-October 2022. <https://www.evidencepartners.com>).

The first step was based on titles and abstracts and the above question was applied to identify the presence of elements in the abstract and title indicating the potential availability of information on physiology, ecology, and distribution of the pest in the full text. In case of positive answer, the type of information potentially available was specified (i.e., Physiology/Ecology, Distribution, or Other) (see Figure 1 as an example).

By selecting the answer “yes”, the reference was automatically moved to the next level of screening (i.e., full text screening). When it was unclear whether information of interest was available from the title and the abstract the answer “unclear” was selected, automatically carrying the paper on to the next step. The second step of the screening (Figure 2) was based on the full text of the documents screened in the first step.

Reference Details

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EFFECTS OF TEMPERATURE AND ADULT AGE ON THE OVIPOSITION RATE OF ELASMOPALPUS-LIGNOSELLUS (ZELLER), THE LESSER CORNSTALK BORER
Mack, T. P., Backman, C. B.
1984
<https://doi.org/10.1093/ee/13.4.966>

Attachments

Full Text Links

DOI.org

Reference Labelist:

WoS_Scopus

No abstract uploaded

Submit Form and go to Datarama order or Skip to Next

1. INHERITED FROM TIAB SCREENING
Selection criteria in tiab
Physiology/Ecology
Distribution
Others

2. Is there any information on physiology, ecology and distribution of the pest?
Yes No Unclear (to be consulted)

3. What type of information
Physiology/Ecology
Distribution
Other

Host

T RH Photoperiod
Yes Yes Yes
Clear Response Clear Response Clear Response

4. Are there any information on the developmental stage of the pest in nature?
Yes No Unclear

Figure 2: Full-text Screening, Screenshot from DistillerSR (DistillerSR. Version 2.35. Evidence Partners; 2021. Accessed September-October 2022. <https://www.evidencepartners.com/>.)

Data extraction

Data extraction was performed on two files for the documents passing the full-text screening. One Excel sheet describing all the relevant information extracted, hereafter referred to as 'Master file' (ANNEX A), and a csv file used to record data on pest distribution (ANNEX B). **Error! Reference source not found.** shows the information extracted from the documents and collected in the Master file.

Table 4: Information extracted from the documents and collected in the master file

Field name	Description	Type
Refid	Record ID. The Refid number is a unique number associated to each reference in Distiller	Integer
Reference	Full reference for the record	String
Physiology_Ecology	Presence of information on physiology and/or ecology (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
Distribution	Presence of information on distribution (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
Other	Presence of additional information that could be of interest. Empty means no information	Boolean
T	Presence of information on temperature (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
RH	Presence of information on humidity or moisture (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
Photoperiod	Presence of information on photoperiod (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean

The distribution file (Table 5) contains data on the reported geographical distribution of the pest. The observations were classified according to the reported organism harmfulness and persistence: the field *Species_status1* is based on the reported harmfulness of the organism (i.e., Pest, Non-Pest,

Unclear), the field *Species_status2* based on the reported persistence of the organism in the observed location (i.e., Persistent, Transient, or Unclear). An additional table associated to the distribution table and including additional notes and information on specific records was also created as a supporting information.

Table 5: Elasmopalpus lignosellus observations extracted from the documents and collected in the distribution file.

Field name	Description	Type
Obs_ID	The Obs_ID is a unique number associated to each collected observation	Integer
Continent	Continent where the organism observation was reported	String
Country	Country where the organism observation was reported	String
State	State where the organism observation was reported	String
Observation	Location of the organism observation as reported in literature	String
Admin.level	FAO GAUL Administrative level of the observation	Integer
Admin.source	Administrative shapefile layer used to identify the area of the organism observation (FAO GAUL or location)	String
Admin.code	FAO GAUL Administrative code of the observation	Integer
Lat	Latitude of the organism observation	Double
Long	Longitude of the organism observation	Double
Google_Earth_Coord	Google Earth coordinates were used to identify the location only if the observation was not available in the FAO GAUL Administrative subdivision and in case of relatively small entities like towns/cities/provinces. Empty means that the coordinates were indicated in the literature or that the location is identified by an administrative layer	Boolean
RefID	Record ID. The RefID is a unique number associated to each reference in Distiller. This is the same field used also in Error! Reference source not found.	Integer
Species_status1	Classifies the organism harmfulness in the area observed (i.e., Pest, Non-Pest, Unclear)	String
Species_status2	Classifies the organism persistence in the area observed (i.e., Persistent, Transient, or Unclear)	String
Notes	Flagged records (with 'x') include additional information saved in the support table	Boolean
Uncertain	Flagged records (with 'x') refer to documents including uncertain information regarding the organism observation (e.g., records from museums, interceptions, not clear information)	Boolean

Climate Classification analysis

The SCAN-Clim tool (EFSA and Maiorano, 2022) was used to produce climate suitability maps based on the climate classification approach. The re-analysis of Rubel et al. (2017) of the Köppen–Geiger climate classification from Kottek et al. (2006), considering the period 1986–2010 (available at <http://koeppen-geiger.vu-wien.ac.at/present.htm>), was used. The climate types present in the observed locations of *Elasmopalpus lignosellus* were identified and mapped. Since the area of the assessment is the EU, the output maps considered only climate types that are present in this area.

CLIMEX parameterization

CLIMEX (version 4.1.0.0) was used to assess the climate suitability of *E. lignosellus*. Simulations were run under the climate dataset CM30 1995H V2 WO (Kriticos et al., 2012), package v4.1 (available at: <https://www.climond.org/>) to calculate the Ecoclimatic Index and degree days. We refer to the related EFSA Pest Risk Assessment for a detailed description of how the CLIMEX model was parameterised (EFSA et al., 2023)

Table 6: CLIMEX parameters for *E. lignosellus*. Parameters highlighted in grey were not adjusted and value already included in the CLIMEX “semi-arid” template were used.

Parameter	Description	value	Min	Max	Sources
Moisture					
SM0	Lower soil moisture threshold	0			(Carrola, 1984); (Mack 1986, 1987, 1988); (Rázuri, 1974); (Sandhu 2010); (Viana, 1995).
SM1	Lower optimal soil moisture	0.03			
SM2	Upper optimal soil moisture	0.8			
SM3	Upper soil moisture threshold	1.6			
Temperature					
DV0	Lower temperature threshold	9 °C	9 °C	13 °C	(Mack et al., 1987); (Sandhu 2010); (Sandhu et al. 2010.)
DV1	Lower optimal temperature	26 °C	25 °C	33 °C	(Holloway and Smith 1976); (Mack et al. 1987); (Sandhu et al. 2010).
DV2	Upper optimal temperature	36 °C	33 °C	36 °C	(Sandhu et al. 2010); (Mack et al., 1987)
DV3	Upper temperature threshold	48 °C	40 °C	48 °C	(Mack and Appel 1986); (Mack et al. 1988).
Cold stress					
TTCS	Cold stress temperature threshold	3 °C			
THCS	Cold stress accumulation rate	-0.003 week ⁻¹			
DTCS	Cold stress will begin to accumulate when this threshold number of degree-days above DVCS is not achieved.				CLIMEX “semi-arid” template
DHCS	Rate at which Cold Stress accumulates once the threshold number of degree-days above DVCS (DTCS) is not achieved				CLIMEX “semi-arid” template
TTCSA	Average weekly temperature below which Cold Stress accumulates.				CLIMEX “semi-arid” template
THCSA	Rate at which Cold Stress accumulates once temperatures drop below the threshold value of TTCS1.				CLIMEX “semi-arid” template
Heat stress					
TTHS	Heat stress temperature threshold	48 °C			
THHS	Heat stress accumulation rate	0.5 week ⁻¹			
DTHS	Heat stress will begin to accumulate when this threshold number of degree-days above DV3 is exceeded.				CLIMEX “semi-arid” template
DHHS	This is the rate at which Heat Stress accumulates once the threshold number of degree-days above DV3 (DTHS) is exceeded				CLIMEX “semi-arid” template
Wet Stress					
SMWS	Soil moisture wet stress threshold	1.6			
HWS	Wet stress accumulation rate	0.005 week ⁻¹			
Threshold Annual Heat sum					
PDD	Minimum degree day sum needed to complete a generation	543 °C days			(Sandhu, 2010)

Additional CLIMEX simulation scenarios

Starting from the reference parameterization, two additional scenarios were run to explore two possible different responses to temperature and wet conditions by decreasing the sensitivity to the cold stress and by increasing the sensitivity to the wet stress respectively (EFSA et al., 2023).

Irrigated scenarios

In order to consider the potential effects of irrigation, two CLIMEX scenarios were run for every parameterization. One was considering no irrigation, the other included the weekly application of a top-up irrigation of 2.5 mm d^{-1} if the same amount was not reached through rainfall. The irrigation scenario was applied only to irrigated areas identified based on Meier et al. (2018) (available at: <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.884744>). Data from Meier et al., (2018) are based on a binary (irrigated vs not irrigated) 0.008° grid. Since CLIMEX simulations are on a 0.5° grid, the data were upscaled to the same resolution of CLIMEX by calculating the percentage of irrigated 0.008° pixels inside each $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$ cell. Based on different threshold percentages (A: $> 0\%$, B: $> 5\%$, C: $> 10\%$, and D: $> 25\%$), Figure 3 shows four distributions of irrigated areas.

Figure 3: Upscaling of irrigation data from Meier et al. (2018) at different percentage levels. Blue areas indicate irrigated pixels. A $0.5 \times 0.5^\circ$ pixel was considered as irrigated if, starting from the top left, and following the direction of the arrows, it contained at least more than 0% (Figure 4A), 5% (Figure 4B), 10% (Figure 4C), or 25% (Figure 4D) of 0.008° irrigated cells.

The distribution of irrigated areas in Figure 3B, was selected and used in the CLIMEX analyses (Figure 4, showing the comparison between the original Meier et al., 2018 map and the one used in CLIMEX).

Figure 4: Comparison between Meier et al. (2018) irrigation map (1) and the upscaled Scenario B (2) used in the analysis. In the figure on the left (1), white areas indicate irrigated pixels, while in the figure on the right (2) blue areas indicate upscaled irrigated pixels. The distribution of irrigated pixels in figure 2 follows the one visible in figure 1.

Climate change scenarios

The potential effects of climate change on the climate suitability of *E. lignosellus* in the EU were analysed for a relatively near-term period (2040 - 2059). The outputs of four regional climate models (i.e., ACCESS 1.0, CNRM-CM5, GFDL-ESM-2M, and NorESM1-M, available at: <https://www.climond.org/Core/Authenticated/ClimeX.aspx>) for the representative emission scenario RCP8.5 (“business as usual”), were used as input in CLIMEX (Kriticos et al., 2012). Model parameterization followed the same specifications as of the current scenario.

Results

This section includes the results and description of the literature search, the data extraction, and the climate suitability analysis. In the present document, only the results of the model simulations are shown. For a detailed description and discussion of the of the climate suitability analysis and its implications in the context of the EFSA quantitative Pest Risk Assessment, please refer to the related scientific opinion (EFSA et al., 2023).

Systematic literature review

Figure 5 shows the PRISMA diagram (Moher et al., 2009) summarizing the results of the systematic literature search. A total of 474 references were found through the searches in Web of Science and Scopus. After the removal of duplicated references, 431 were imported as compressed EndNote library (.enlx) in the software DistillerSR. Seventy-one additional papers retrieved from grey literature were added to the pool. In total, 502 reference were screened through a title and abstract selection. Of these, 109 were excluded and the full text of the remaining 393 references was analysed. Ninety-eight references were excluded by the full text screening because of i.e., the absence of relevant information or the impossibility to find the full text document. Data were then extracted from 295 documents. Out of these, 271 contained information on the distribution of *E. lignosellus*, while 65 contained information on its eco-physiology.

PRISMA 2009 Flow Diagram

Figure 5: PRISMA Diagram describing the process followed to identify, screen, and include eligible information on the ecology, physiology, and distribution of the pest *Elasmopalpus lignosellus*.

Observed distribution

The literature search yielded 588 records of observation at both point locations (coordinates) and administrative level. All the records are available in the observations file (ANNEX B) and displayed in Figure 6. From the observed distribution, 261 are point locations, reporting specific coordinates or small administrative units (e.g., US counties) for which either the coordinates indicated in the paper or the coordinates from Google Earth (<https://earth.google.com/web/>) were used. The remaining 327 observations are administrative units (e.g., countries, regions) identified through their FAO Global Administrative Unit Layer (GAUL) codes (https://developers.google.com/earth-engine/datasets/catalog/FAO_GAUL_2015_level1).

Figure 6: Observed distribution of *E. lignosellus*. The map on the left (A) shows point observations (with coordinates) where the pest was reported. The map on the right (B) shows the distribution at the administrative unit level (FAO GAUL).

Köppen–Geiger climate matching

Figure 7: World distribution of Köppen–Geiger climate types also present in Europe where *E. lignosellus* was observed. Red dots indicate point observations of the pest (coordinates). Climates not present in EU are not mapped. Legend shows the lists of Köppen–Geiger climate type shown in the map.

Figure 8: World distribution of Köppen–Geiger climate types also present in Europe where *E. lignosellus* was observed **without** the temperate oceanic climate (Cfb). Red dots indicate point observations of the pest (coordinates). Climates not present in EU are not mapped. Legend shows the lists of Köppen-Geiger climate types shown in the map.

CLIMEX simulations under current climate

CLIMEX Ecoclimatic Index (EI) for Elasmopalpus lignosellus with top-up irrigation.

Figure 9: CLIMEX Ecoclimatic Index (EI) for *Elasmopalpus lignosellus* across the Americas, in Europe, and northern Africa. The simulation was made **with** top-up irrigation. Darker colors suggest more favorable conditions for establishment (higher EI).

CLIMEX Ecoclimatic Index (EI) for *Elasmopalpus lignosellus* without top-up irrigation.

Figure 10: CLIMEX Ecoclimatic Index (EI) for *Elasmopalpus lignosellus* across the Americas, in Europe, and northern Africa. The simulation was made **without** top-up irrigation. Darker colors suggest more favorable conditions for establishment (higher EI).

CLIMEX Ecoclimatic Index (EI) for *Elasmopalpus lignosellus*, lower cold stress scenario with irrigation.

Figure 11: Lower cold stress with irrigation. Maps of CLIMEX Ecoclimatic Index (EI) for *Elasmopalpus lignosellus* of the Americas, the EU, and northern Africa. The simulation is based on parameters given in Table 6 but with a lower cold stress (see **Error! Not a valid bookmark self-reference.**) in an irrigated scenario. Darker colors suggest more favorable conditions for establishment (higher EI).

CLIMEX Ecoclimatic Index (EI) for *Elasmopalpus lignosellus*, higher wet stress scenario with irrigation.

Figure 12: Higher wet stress with irrigation. Maps of CLIMEX Ecoclimatic Index (EI) for *Elasmopalpus lignosellus* of the Americas, the EU, and northern Africa. The simulation is based on parameters given in Table 6 but with a higher wet stress (see *Error! Not a valid bookmark self-reference.*) in an irrigated scenario. Darker colors suggest more favorable conditions for establishment (higher EI).

CLIMEX simulations under climate change

Figure 13: The increased area with an EI > 30 of the four climate change models and their average (in red) compared to the current scenario (in yellow). The four figures on the left represent the results of the four climate change models used in CLIMEX (starting from the top left: ACCESS 1.0, CNRM-CM5, GFDL-ESM-2M, and NorESM1-M). The figure on the right is the average of the four climate change models compared to the current conditions

Degree-days accumulation

Degree days maps for Americas and Europe in the current climate scenario.

Figure 14: Degree days maps for Americas and Europe in the current climate scenario. Figures A1 and A2 were created with a base temperature of 9°C while figures B1 and B2 with a base temperature of 13°C.

Degree days maps for Americas and Europe in the climate change scenario.

Figure 15: Degree days maps for Americas and Europe in the climate change scenario (average of the four CC models). Figures A1 and A2 were created with a base temperature of 9°C while figures B1 and B2 with a base temperature of 13°C.

Content of the *Elasmopalpus lignosellus* Zenodo repository

[Elasmopalpus_lignosellus_ClimateSuitability_Report.pdf](#)

The file contains the methodology and results of the literature search used for the Climate Suitability Analysis of *Elasmopalpus lignosellus*. The results of the databases interrogations are presented together with the process applied for documents screening and selection, summarised by a PRISMA diagram. The CLIMEX parameterization of the irrigated and not irrigated scenarios are presented and maps illustrate the results of the climate suitability analysis. Although, we refer to the related PRA for an exhaustive and more comprehensive discussion of the results of the climate suitability analysis.

[Elasmopalpus_lignosellus_ANNEX_A_Master_file.xlsx](#)

The file contains the list of documents selected for data extraction. The description of the fields is in [Elasmopalpus_lignosellus_ClimateSuitability_Report.pdf](#).

[Elasmopalpus_lignosellus_ANNEX_B_Observations.csv](#)

The file contains the list of the organism observed distribution at a global level. Both point locations and administrative units are included.

Maps in .png format

- CLIMEX_EI_Avg_4_CC_models.png
- CLIMEX_EI_higher_wet_stress_irrigated.png
- CLIMEX_EI_higher_wet_stress_irrigated.png
- CLIMEX_EI_lower_cold_stress_irrigated.png
- CLIMEX_EI_not_irrigated_scenario.png
- KG_Europe_Americas_Cfb.png
- KG_Europe_Americas_no_Cfb.png
- Koppen_Geiger_Cfb.png
- Koppen_Geiger_no_Cfb.png
- Observations.png
- Increased_Risk_Area_CC.png

[Resseliella_citrifrugis_PRA.gpkg](#)

This is a GeoPackage (.gpkg) file containing the GIS layers of the results of the analysis.

References

- Devorshak C, 2012. Plant pest risk analysis: concepts and applications.
- EFSA, 2010. Application of systematic review methodology to food and feed safety assessments to support decision making. *EFSA journal*, 8:1637
- EFSA, Health PoP, Bragard C, Baptista P, Chatzivassiliou E, Di Serio F, Gonthier P, Jaques Miret JA, Justesen AF, MacLeod A, Magnusson CS, Milonas P, Navas-Cortes JA, Parnell S, Potting R, Reignault PL, Stefani E, Thulke H-H, Vicent Civera A, Yuen J, Zappalà L, Mally R, Czwienczek E, Maiorano A, Mosbach-Schulz O, Pautasso M, Stancanelli G, Tramontini S and Van der Werf W, 2023. Pest risk assessment of *Elasmopalpus lignosellus* for the European Union. *EFSA journal*, 21:e08004. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2023.8004>
- EFSA and Maiorano A, 2022. SCAN-Clim: a tool to support pest climate suitability analysis based on climate classification. *EFSA journal*, 20:e07104
- Evidence Partners, 2022. DistillerSR. 2.35 Edition. Place Distiller Inc, Distiller Inc.
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